

Lay health workers in primary and community health care for chronic conditions

Protocol for a Cochrane review update

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Background

Description of the condition

The primary healthcare approach adopted by the World Health Organization (WHO) and UNICEF at Alma-Ata promoted the initiation and rapid expansion of lay (community) health workers (LHW) programmes in low and middle income country (LMIC) settings in the 1970s, including a number of large national programmes [1]. However, the effectiveness and cost of such programmes came to be questioned in the following decade, particularly at a national level in LMICs. Several evaluations were conducted and these indicated difficulties in the scaling up of LHW programmes, as a consequence of a number of factors. Important constraints included inadequate training and on-going supervision; insecure funding for and availability of incentives, equipment and essential medicines; failure to integrate LHW initiatives with the formal health system; poor planning for implementation; and opposition from health professionals [1, 2]. These constraints led to poor quality care and difficulties in retaining trained LHWs in many of the programmes. However, most of these early evaluations were uncontrolled case studies that could not produce robust assessments of effectiveness.

The 1990s saw renewed interest in LHW programmes in LMICs. This was prompted by a number of factors including the AIDS epidemic; the resurgence of other infectious diseases such as tuberculosis; and the failure of the formal health system to provide adequate care for people with chronic conditions [3, 4]. The growing emphasis on decentralisation and partnership with community-based organisations also contributed to this renewed interest. In high income country settings, a perceived need for mechanisms to deliver health care to minority communities and to support people with a wide range of health conditions led to further growth in a wide range of LHW interventions [5, 6]. A growing number of these LHW programmes were evaluated in randomised trials [7].

More recently, the greater focus on the human resource crisis in health care in many settings has re-energised debates regarding the roles that LHWs may play in extending services to 'hard to reach' groups and areas and in substituting for health professionals for a range of tasks [8-12]. The COVID-19 pandemic has further highlighted the important roles that LHWs can play in helping to ensure access to health information and to health care [13-15]. Human resource shortages in the health services are widely acknowledged as a threat to the attainment of health-related Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) [16, 17]. Attempts to optimize the potential of the existing health workforce are therefore crucial. A more rational distribution of tasks and responsibilities among cadres of health workers is seen as a promising strategy for improving access and cost-effectiveness within health systems [11, 18, 19].

Although LHWs have been extensively implemented and evaluated in the area of maternal and child health, the heavy burden of chronic conditions in LMICs has shifted recent discussions towards the issue of human resources for delivering health services to people living with these conditions. Shared features of these conditions include that:

- Many have their origins at young ages
- Given their long duration, there are many opportunities for prevention
- They require a long-term and systematic approach to prevention, treatment and support
- Health services need to integrate responses to these conditions with elements of primary health care.

In this context, LHWs have been identified as one strategy to address the growing shortage of health workers for managing chronic conditions in primary and community care. Given the substantial costs of managing chronic conditions, finding effective and efficient ways of identifying and supporting people living with these conditions is becoming increasingly important for health systems.

Description of the intervention

LHWs could perform diverse roles and tasks related to health care delivery. While there are many different definitions of what constitutes a LHW, the term is used here with a broad definition and scope, and includes community health workers, village health workers, treatment supporters, peer coaches, peer counsellors, peer educators and birth attendants. For the purposes of this review, we have defined a LHW as any health worker who performs functions related to healthcare delivery; was trained in some way in the context of this care delivery; but has received no formal professional certificate or tertiary education degree [20]. LHWs may be paid or work on a voluntary basis and may be employed and managed by a wide range of organisations, including publicly funded health departments, NGOs and community-based organisations.

How the intervention might work

In a previous qualitative evidence synthesis [21], we developed several logic models that hypothesise how factors affecting the implementation of LHW programmes might impact on the outcomes of these programmes (see figures 4 and 5 in [21]). Although this evidence is from the maternal and child health field, we think that most of the relationships could be extrapolated to the use of LHWs to improve health care access for chronic conditions. Three of these models are particularly relevant for this review.

The first model suggests that where a LHW programme is integrated with, or works closely with, the formal health system, healthcare professionals are more likely to be aware of and make use of LHW services, and healthcare professionals and LHWs are more likely to collaborate. This, in turn, can improve working relationships between LHWs and the healthcare professional. Improved relationships can lead to more appropriate and effective referrals to and from LHWs, and may increase LHWs' ability and willingness to deliver services to clients. Over time, this can result in services of higher quality and in better health outcomes [21].

The second model focuses on the working conditions, training and supervision of LHWs, and suggests a number of factors that may increase their willingness and ability to provide services. This, in turn, can lead to better quality services and to improved health outcomes. These factors relate to whether LHWs perceive their incentives as appropriate and fair in relation to the training they have received and the work that they are asked to do; whether LHWs have a suitable career pathway; and whether they have opportunities to share their experiences with other LHWs. The model also identifies as important whether LHWs have good physical working conditions and adequate supplies of commodities; whether they see their workload as reasonable, and have manageable distances to cover to reach clients; and whether they have systems through which they can voice any complaints they may have. Other factors include the extent to which LHWs receive appropriate, high-quality training and have access to supervisory support.

The third model focuses on how LHWs are selected, suggesting that where LHWs are selected because they live in the community in which the service will be delivered, because they have similar social backgrounds to service recipients, or because they are living successfully with the same chronic condition as recipients, this may lead to stronger relationships between LHWs and those using their services. This, in turn, may increase the uptake of LHW services and ultimately improve health outcomes. In this model, it is also important whether LHWs are seen by service recipients to exhibit characteristics such as trustworthiness, respect for service recipients and their families, kindness and empathy.

Why it is important to do this review

The wider use of LHWs to provide care and support to people at risk of, or living with, chronic health conditions may improve access to care through decentralising prevention, treatment and support to primary care and community levels. It may also allow other cadres, such as nurses and doctors, to focus on care for people with more complex problems who need more specialised interventions. Further, the use of LHWs may make care more people-centred as LHWs, who come from the same social background as their clients, have extensive local knowledge to better understand clients' needs and to communicate effectively with clients over time [21, 22]. The wider use of LHWs may also help to engage and empower individuals and communities to participate actively in managing their own chronic health conditions and in decisions around the provision of health services. More active self-management is associated with better health outcomes [23].

LHW programmes therefore have the potential to play a critical role in scaling up care and support for people at risk of, or living with, chronic conditions. However, the extent to which these programmes are able to achieve this goal, and which LHW healthcare delivery models are likely to be most effective, feasible and acceptable, needs to be evaluated rigorously. It is important to understand, firstly, whether LHWs can effectively deliver care and support to people at risk of, or living with, chronic health conditions, including for which health tasks (such as prevention, disease surveillance, diagnosis, referral for care, treatment and treatment support) and for which common health conditions (such as diabetes, hypertension, and asthma) they are most effective. Secondly, we need to understand the factors that make LHW programmes effective and facilitate their implementation at scale.

A number of systematic reviews have been conducted on the effectiveness of LHWs for different chronic conditions [24-27]. However, most of these reviews have important limitations: firstly, some consider the use of LHWs for specific chronic conditions only – for example, support of people with asthma [28] or to increase cancer knowledge screening [29] – or for specific components of chronic illness care – for instance, education and treatment support for people living with diabetes [30]. Other reviews are limited by geographic setting considering, for example, studies undertaken in specific countries [31] or regions [32]. Because these subgroups of the wider population of effectiveness studies on LHWs generally include only small numbers of studies, their results may be misleading. Secondly, some of the reviews do not use robust approaches, such as GRADE, to assess the certainty of their findings [33]. This limits the usefulness of their findings for informing decisions. Finally, a number of these reviews are several years old and so do not reflect the full body of knowledge that is available currently.

Objectives

To assess the effects of lay health worker interventions in primary and community health care for chronic conditions.¹

Methods

Criteria for considering studies for this review

Types of studies

Individual and cluster randomised controlled trials. Cluster randomised trials will need to have a least two intervention and two control sites to be included [34]. We will include studies irrespective of their publication status and language.

¹ A parallel review update will assess the effects of LHW interventions in primary and community care for maternal and child health and infectious diseases. We decided to divide the review in this way as the number of eligible randomised trials is now very large and it is not feasible to include all of these in one review update.

Types of participants

Types of healthcare providers

Any LHW, including paid or unpaid LHWs. For the purposes of this review, we define the term lay health worker as any health worker who:

- performed functions related to any aspect of healthcare delivery (including health promotion, screening, and providing and supporting treatment),
- was trained in some way in the context of the intervention, but
- had received no formal professional certificate or tertiary education degree [20].

We will include interventions if the description is detailed enough to establish that it is an intervention delivered by a LHW. Where this is unclear, we will attempt to contact the trial authors to establish whether the health workers described were LHWs.

In previous versions of this review [7], one of the inclusion criteria for LHWs was that they had received no formal paraprofessional certificate. However, this criterion has become difficult to operationalise as LHWs in some contexts are now provided with certified training (for example: [35]). We have therefore amended our inclusion criteria to define a LHW as a health worker who has not received *professional* certification, for example from a statutory certifying body such as a Health Professions Council. LHWs may receive some certification but cannot be registered with a certifying body for health professionals.

We will also include trials in which the LHWs deliver support on the telephone or online (as part of a digital health intervention), or help people to use information that is available online.

Exclusions

We will exclude interventions in which a healthcare function was performed as an extension to a participant's profession (for example teachers providing health promotion in schools). We define the term 'profession' as remunerated work for which formal tertiary education is required.

We will not consider formally trained nurse aides, medical assistants, physician assistants, paramedical workers in emergency and fire services, and other self-defined health professionals or health paraprofessionals. We will also exclude trainee health professionals and trainees of any of the cadres listed above.

We will also exclude interventions:

- involving patient support groups only. These interventions are seen as different to LHW interventions in that the lay people involved meet only to provide each other with informal support rather than to provide care or services to others, and also seldom receive training in the context of the intervention;
- involving teachers delivering health promotion or related activities in schools. We reasoned that this large and important system of LHWs constitutes a unique group (teachers) and setting (schools) that, due to the scale and importance, would be better addressed in a separate systematic review;
- involving peer health counselling programmes in schools, in which pupils teach other pupils about health issues as part of the school curriculum. Again, we reasoned that this type of intervention contains a unique group and setting that is better suited to a separate review;
- in which the LHW was a family member trained to deliver care and provide support only to members of his or her own family (that is, in which LHWs did not provide some sort of care or service to others, or were unavailable to other members of the community). These interventions were assessed as qualitatively different from other LHW interventions included in this review given that parents or spouses have an established close relationship with those receiving care which could affect the process and effects of the intervention.

All of these interventions target 'closed' groups of clients – that is, clients who, for the purposes of the intervention, are not part of the general population.

We will also exclude:

- LHWs in non-primary level institutions (e.g. referral hospitals);
- Randomised trials of interventions to train self-management tutors who are health professionals rather than lay persons. Furthermore, trials that compare lay self-management with other forms of management (i.e. those that did not focus on the training of tutors) will also be excluded as these are concerned with the effects of empowering people to manage their own health issues rather than with the effects of interventions using LHWs. These studies are the subject of another Cochrane review [36]. Trials of interventions to train self-management tutors who are themselves lay persons are eligible for inclusion in this review;
- 'Head-to-head' comparisons of different LHW interventions. We decided that these should be reviewed separately as they address the question of the relative effectiveness of different types of LHW interventions rather than the question of the effects of LHWs compared to other types of intervention;
- Multi-faceted interventions that include LHWs and professionals working together and do not include a comparison group that enabled us to separately assess the effects of the LHW intervention;
- Multi-faceted interventions that include LHWs and other types of interventions (such as online educational materials for service users or improved access to medicines) and do not include a comparison group that enabled us to separately assess the effects of the LHW intervention;
- Randomised trials of LHW interventions for the promotion of mental health and wellbeing and for the prevention and treatment of mental illness. These areas are covered by other forthcoming Cochrane reviews and updates [37, 38].

Types of recipients

People at risk of or living with chronic health conditions and their informal caregivers, such as family members. By chronic health conditions, we mean “health problems that require ongoing management over a period of years or decades” – in other words, they continue over time and need at least some level of intervention to manage them ([39] p11). Examples of chronic health conditions include cardiovascular diseases, cancers, diabetes and auto-immune diseases.

Types of interventions

Any intervention delivered by LHWs and intended to improve any aspect of care for people at risk of or with chronic health conditions. Where it is unclear if the health issue addressed in a trial is a chronic condition, we will discuss this among the review authors to reach a consensus. If necessary, we will contact the trial authors to obtain further information or obtain advice from an expert in that area of chronic conditions.

Types of outcome measures

We will include studies if they assess any of the following primary and secondary outcomes.

Primary outcomes categories

1. Health behaviours, such as the type of care plan agreed and people’s adherence to care plans (medication, dietary advice etc.)
2. Healthcare outcomes as assessed by a variety of measures. These include mortality; physiological measures; and participants' self reports of symptom resolution, quality of life, or patient self-esteem
3. Harms or adverse effects

4. Equity impacts in relation to any of the outcomes above

Secondary outcomes categories

1. Utilisation of services
2. Consultation processes, such as how healthcare providers interacted with healthcare users
3. Recipients' satisfaction with care
4. Social development measures, such as the creation of support groups for the promotion of other community activities
5. Increased demand for improved services, such as more appropriate opening hours, better quality of care, or care that is more patient centred

We will exclude studies that measure only recipients' knowledge, attitudes, or intentions. These measures are not considered to be useful indicators of the effectiveness of LHW interventions. For included studies, we will not extract data on recipients' knowledge, attitudes or intentions, for the same reason.

For many of the primary and secondary outcome categories above, randomised trials in each main chronic disease area (such as diabetes or cardiovascular disease) are likely to both assess a wide range of outcomes at a range of timepoints, and use diverse tools to measure these outcomes. To make data extraction and analysis both manageable and meaningful, we will need to prioritise those outcomes that stakeholders, including clinicians, people at risk of or living with the chronic conditions and service managers, view as most important. For each chronic disease area, we will convene a small group of stakeholders to examine the range of outcomes assessed by the included trials; review any global core outcome sets relevant to LHW interventions in the chronic disease area, as compiled by the COMET (Core Outcomes Measures in Effectiveness Trials) Initiative (www.comet-initiative.org); and, based on these, provide guidance on which specific outcomes and assessment timepoints should be prioritized for this review update. This a priori prioritization of outcomes and timepoints will then guide data extraction and analysis.

Electronic searches

For this update, we will search the following electronic databases for primary studies:

- MEDLINE, Ovid
- Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL), part of Cochrane Library, Wiley
- CINAHL, EBSCO
- Global Index Medicus, WHO (www.globalindexmedicus.net/)

Search strategies will incorporate a modified version of the Cochrane Highly Sensitive Search Strategy (sensitivity- and precision-maximizing version - 2008 revision [40]) to identify randomised trials together with selected index terms and free text terms relating to LHWs. We will translate the MEDLINE search strategy for use in the other databases using the appropriate controlled vocabulary, as applicable. We will revise search strategies from the original review to reflect our improved knowledge, following previous versions of this review, of terms used in the literature to describe LHW interventions. We will tailor the search strategy to each database and performed a sensitivity analysis to ensure that most of the relevant studies retrieved during earlier review versions are retrieved again. A draft MEDLINE search strategy is shown in Appendix 1.

Searching other resources

Trial registries:

- WHO ICTRP (World Health Organization International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (www.who.int/ictrp))
- ClinicalTrials.gov, US National Institutes of Health (NIH) (www.clinicaltrials.gov)

Databases of systematic reviews:

We will search PDQ-Evidence, Epistemonikos Foundation, for relevant systematic reviews.

We will review reference lists of all included studies and relevant systematic reviews for additional potentially eligible primary studies. We will contact authors of included studies/reviews to clarify reported published information and to seek unpublished results/data. We will provide appendices for all search strategies used.

Data collection and analysis

Selection of studies

We will download all titles and abstracts retrieved by electronic searching to a reference management database and remove duplicates. Two review authors will assess independently the potential relevance of all titles and abstracts identified from the electronic searches. We will retrieve full text copies of the articles identified as potentially relevant by either one or both review authors. Two review authors will independently screen the full-text and identify studies for inclusion and identify and record reasons for exclusion of the ineligible studies. When review authors disagree, a discussion will be held to obtain consensus. If no agreement is reached, a third review author will be asked to make an independent assessment. Where appropriate, we will contact trial authors for further information and clarification.

We will list studies that initially appeared to meet the inclusion criteria but that we later excluded in the 'Characteristics of excluded studies' table. We will also provide any information we can obtain about ongoing studies. This information will be obtained through simple searching on Google Scholar and Pubmed, and we will not attempt to contact the authors of ongoing studies for further information. We will record the selection process in sufficient detail to complete a PRISMA flow diagram [41].

Data extraction and management

We will extract data using a standard form developed for the previous versions of this review that focused on maternal and child health, and adapted for this review. The adapted form will be piloted on at least two randomised trials, and changes made as needed. One review author will extract all outcome data from included studies and a second review author will check these data. Any outstanding uncertainties will be discussed by the data extractors and resolved by consensus. Where contact information is available, we will make up to three attempts to contact primary trial authors to obtain any missing information.

We will extract the following data from all included studies:

1. **Methods:** whether the trial was individual or cluster randomised (for cluster randomised trials, we will extract data on the unit of randomisation), number of study centres and location, study setting, date of study, follow-up.
2. **Participants:** for LHWs this includes terms used to describe the LHW, basic education, and tasks performed. For recipients, these data will include the health problems, their age and demographic details, and their employment status.
3. **Context:** The healthcare setting (home, primary care facility, or other), the geographic setting (rural, urban, both, not specified) and country.
4. **Intervention:** specific training and ongoing monitoring and support (including duration, methods, who delivered the training, etc.), and the healthcare tasks performed with recipients.
5. **Outcomes:** main and other outcomes specified and collected, time points reported. Where both objective and subjective measures are available for the same outcomes, we will extract both of

these. Extraction of data on outcomes will also be guided by the guidance emerging from the stakeholder consultations described above.

6. Factors related to the planned subgroup analyses described in Table 1.
7. Notes: funding sources of the trial, notable conflicts of interest of trial authors, ethical approval

Assessment of risk of bias in included studies

One review author will assess risk of bias for each study using the criteria outlined in the *Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions* Section 8.5 [42], and the guidance from the EPOC group [43]. A second review author will check these assessments. We will resolve any disagreements by discussion or by involving a third review author. We will assess the risk of bias according to the following domains:

1. Random sequence generation
2. Allocation concealment, including whether cluster randomised trials completed allocation on all units before recruiting participants
3. Blinding of participants and personnel (performance bias)²
4. Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)
5. Incomplete outcome data
6. Selective outcome reporting
7. Baseline outcomes measurement
8. Baseline characteristics
9. Protection against contamination
10. Other bias

We will judge each potential source of bias as high, low, or unclear and provide a quote from the study report together with a justification for our judgement in the 'Risk of bias' table. We will summarise the 'Risk of bias' judgements across different studies for each of the domains listed. We will assign an overall 'Risk of bias' assessment (high, moderate or low) to each of the included studies using the approach suggested in Chapter 8 of the *Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions* [42]. We will consider studies with low risk of bias for all key domains or where it seems unlikely for bias to seriously alter the results, to have a low risk of bias. We will consider studies where risk of bias in at least one domain was unclear or judged to have some bias that could plausibly raise doubts about the conclusions, to have an unclear risk of bias. We will consider studies with a high risk of bias in at least one domain or judged to have serious bias that decreases the certainty of the conclusions, to have a high risk of bias.

We will consider blinding separately for different key outcomes where necessary (e.g. for unblinded outcome assessment, risk of bias for all-cause mortality may be very different than for a patient reported pain scale). Where information on risk of bias relates to unpublished data or correspondence with a trialist, we will note this in the 'Risk of bias' table. We will not exclude studies on the grounds of their risk of bias, but will clearly report the risk of bias when presenting the results of the studies.

When considering treatment effects, we will take into account the risk of bias for the studies that contribute to that outcome.

² This item is not specified in the EPOC RoB guidance, but will be assessed as follows:

- low risk of bias: study has a clear statement that participants, carers, and personnel were unaware of intervention allocation, and ideally describes how this was achieved
- unclear risk of bias: unclear whether participants, carers, and personnel were blind to intervention allocation
- high risk of bias: studies where intervention allocation is not blinded

Measures of treatment effect

Measures of effect will depend on the type of data presented in the individual studies for specific outcomes. We will use risk ratio (RR) for dichotomous data, together with the appropriate associated 95% confidence interval, and mean difference (MD) or standardised mean difference (SMD) for continuous data, together with the appropriate associated 95% confidence interval [42]. We will ensure that an increase in scores for continuous outcomes can be interpreted in the same way for each outcome, explain the direction to the reader, and report where the directions were reversed, if this was necessary.

Unit of analysis issues

Studies that allocate groups of participants (e.g. by village) should account for clustering during analysis, in order to prevent unit of analysis errors. We will consider data to have been analysed appropriately if either:

1. the analysis was conducted at the same level as the allocation (i.e. at the 'cluster' level);
2. the usual analysis was used but the sample size was reduced to its 'effective sample size' or the variance was inflated by the design effect; or
3. the analysis was conducted at the level of the individual, but appropriate statistical correction for the clustering was performed (such as generalised estimating equations (GEE), mixed models, or multilevel models).

Where studies are not analysed appropriately, we will make adjustments for clustering following the method suggested in the Cochrane Handbook [42]. Where no information on the intra-cluster correlation coefficient (ICC) is reported in any of the cluster RCTs included in the analysis group, we will assume an ICC of 0.02 for this adjustment. This ICC is typical of primary and community care interventions [44]. Where an ICC is reported among the studies in a group, this ICC will be used for the adjustments to other studies.

We will calculate log relative risks (RR) and standard errors (SE) of the log RR for both individual and cluster RCTs (unadjusted). Then we will adjust the unadjusted SEs for cluster RCTs for the effect of clustering using the multiplicative factor square root of the design effect ($= (1 + (\text{mean cluster size} - 1) * \text{ICC}))$).

Dealing with missing data

We will attempt to contact authors to obtain important missing information. Where necessary, we will try to compute missing summary data from other reported statistics. Whenever it is not possible to obtain data, we will report the level of missingness and consider how that might impact the certainty of the evidence.

Assessment of heterogeneity

We will assess clinical heterogeneity by preparing tables that summarize the study characteristics (types of participants, interventions, outcomes, and study design). This will allow us to examine the similarity between the studies regarding relevant factors.

If we find a sufficient number of studies, where we judge participants, interventions, comparisons and outcomes to be sufficiently similar, we will conduct a meta-analysis [45]. For comparisons with a sufficient number of studies to undertake a meta-analysis, we will use the Chi² test and the I² statistic to measure heterogeneity (we will consider a P value of less than 0.05 or an I² value equal to or more than 50% as indicating substantial heterogeneity). If we identify substantial heterogeneity we will explore it by prespecified subgroup analysis [42].

Assessment of reporting biases

We will attempt to minimise reporting bias by:

- including both published and unpublished studies;
- in the case of studies with multiple publications, extracting data on outcomes from the publication with the most mature data;
- not excluding studies solely on the basis of the publication language; and
- contacting trial authors to provide missing outcome data. Where this is not possible, and the missing data are thought to introduce serious bias, we will explore the impact of including such studies in the overall assessment of results.

If we are able to pool more than 10 trials, we will create and examine a funnel plot to explore possible publication bias, interpreting the results with caution [46].

Data synthesis

We will group together studies according to the type of health issue addressed by the LHWs (e.g. LHW interventions to promote breast cancer screening). We will undertake meta-analyses only where this is meaningful (i.e. if the treatments, participants, and the underlying clinical question are similar enough for pooling to make sense [45]) and feasible. Where multiple trial arms are reported in a single trial, we will include only the relevant arms. If two comparisons (e.g. intervention A versus usual care and intervention B versus usual care) must be entered into the same meta-analysis, we will halve the control group to avoid double-counting.

As we anticipate important heterogeneity, we will plan to use a random-effects model meta-analysis. We will analyse the log RRs for individual RCTs and the adjusted log RRs for cluster RCTs together, using the generic inverse variance method in Review Manager 5.

Where it is not possible to meta-analyse the data we will summarise the results narratively, using the relevant guidance [47].

'Summary of findings' and GRADE

Two review authors will independently assess the certainty of the evidence (high, moderate, low, and very low) using the five GRADE considerations: risk of bias, consistency of effect, imprecision, indirectness, and publication bias [48]. We will use methods and recommendations described in Section 8.5 and Chapter 12 of the *Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of interventions* [42], and the EPOC worksheets [49], and we will use GRADEpro software (GRADEpro GDT). We will resolve disagreements on certainty ratings by discussion and provide justification for decisions to down- or upgrade the ratings using footnotes in the table and make comments to aid readers' understanding of the review where necessary. We will use plain language statements to report these findings in the review [49].

We will summarise the findings in a 'Summary of findings' table(s) for each intervention comparison, and include the primary outcomes and the certainty of the evidence. If during the review process, we become aware of an important outcome that we failed to list in our planned 'Summary of findings' table(s), we will include the relevant outcome and explain the reasons for this in the section 'Differences between protocol and review'.

We will consider whether there is any additional outcome information that was not able to be incorporated into meta-analyses and note this in the comments and state if it supports or contradicts the information from the meta-analyses.

Subgroup analysis and investigation of heterogeneity

Based on the findings of a qualitative evidence synthesis related to this review [21], we will use the following characteristics of LHW programmes to perform a number of subgroups analysis, where feasible:

Table 1: Planned subgroup analyses

Factors identified in the qualitative evidence synthesis [21]	Hypothesis on how these impact on outcomes of LHW interventions
Level of collaboration between individual lay health workers and health professionals (linkage to the healthcare system)	Close / more effective collaboration between LHWs and health professionals may facilitate more seamless referral, sharing of information and support
Whether the LHWs were paid or received other specific resources/incentives	LHWs who receive consistent and predictable incentives that they regard as appropriate and fair in relation to their tasks and level of training may be more likely to perform optimally
Sufficient, relevant, high quality training, including in counseling and communication	LHWs who are appropriately trained may be more likely to perform optimally
Adequate skilled supervision received	LHWs who receive adequate skilled supervision may be more likely to perform optimally

In addition, we will assess the effect of the following study characteristics on the magnitude of the effect:

- Sample size: large versus small studies defined by the number of LHWs delivering the intervention or the size of the population receiving the intervention (recipients).
- Study setting: high-, middle- or low-income countries based on the World Bank Classification [50].

Sensitivity analysis

We will perform sensitivity analyses defined a priori to assess the robustness of our conclusions and explore its impact on effect sizes. This will involve the following:

1. Restricting the analysis to published studies.
2. Restricting the analysis to studies with a low risk of bias, as specified above.

We will conduct the review according to this published protocol and report any deviations from it in the 'Differences between protocol and review' section of the systematic review.

Contributions of authors

Conceiving the protocol: SL, SMB, TP

Designing the protocol: SL, SMB, TP

Designing search strategies: MJ, with input from SL, SMB, TP

Writing the protocol: SL, SMB, TP

Editing and approval of the protocol: all authors

Securing funding for the protocol: SL

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Declarations of interest

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Internal sources

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Appendix 1: MEDLINE draft search strategy

#	Searches
1	Community Health Workers/
2	Doulas/
3	((lay adj worker?) or (lay adj health* worker?) or (lay adj health care worker?)).ti,ab.
4	(lay adj3 (counselor? or counsellor? or counseling or counselling or coach* or intervention? or support or outreach or delivered or staff or led or provider? or based or volunteer? or mentor* or educator? or visitor? or adviser? or advisor? or facilitator? or person*)).ti,ab.
5	(community worker? or community health* worker? or community health care worker? or community volunteer?).ti,ab.
6	(community based worker? or community based health* worker? or community based health care worker? or community based volunteer?).ti,ab.
7	(village worker? or village health* worker? or village health care worker?).ti,ab.
8	(village based worker? or village based health* worker? or village based health care worker?).ti,ab.
9	((peer adj worker?) or (peer adj health* worker?) or (peer adj health care worker?)).ti,ab.
10	(peer adj (counselor? or counsellor? or counseling or counselling or coach* or intervention? or support or outreach or delivered or staff or led or provider? or based or volunteer? or mentor* or educator? or visitor? or adviser? or advisor? or facilitator? or personnel)).ti,ab.
11	((non professional? or nonprofessional? or paraprofessional?) adj3 (counselor? or counsellor? or counseling or counselling or coach* or intervention? or support or outreach or delivered or staff or led or provider? or based or volunteer? or mentor* or educator? or visitor? or adviser? or advisor? or facilitator? or personnel)).ti,ab.
12	(volunteer? adj3 (counselor? or counsellor? or counseling or counselling or coach* or intervention? or support or outreach or delivered or staff or led or provider? or based or mentor* or educator? or visitor? or adviser? or advisor?)).ti,ab.
13	((outreach or support or family) adj worker*).ti,ab.
14	(birth attendan* or doula or doulas).ti,ab.
15	((parent* or mother?) adj3 (mentor* or facilitator?)).ti,ab.
16	(trained adj3 (mother? or case manager? or leader?)).ti,ab.
17	((support adj (intervention? or program*)) and (community based or telephone or phone or volunteer? or women* or mother? or maternal or pregnancy or parent? or child or children or infant?)).ti,ab.
18	((home visit* or household visit*) adj3 (intervention? or program* or condition or non professional? or nonprofessional? or paraprofessional? or volunteer?)).ti,ab.
19	(home treatment and mother?).ti,ab.
20	(home based adj3 intervention?).ti,ab.
21	(social network? adj3 intervention?).ti,ab.
22	(participatory adj3 women's group?).ti,ab.
23	task shift*.ti,ab.
24	or/1-23
25	randomized controlled trial.pt.
26	controlled clinical trial.pt.
27	(randomized or randomised).ti,ab.
28	randomly.ab.
29	trial.ab.
30	groups.ab.
31	or/25-30
32	exp Animals/
33	Humans/

34	32 not (32 and 33)
35	review.pt.
36	meta analysis.pt.
37	news.pt.
38	comment.pt.
39	editorial.pt.
40	cochrane database of systematic reviews.jn.
41	comment on.cm.
42	systematic review.pt.
43	(systematic review or literature review).ti.
44	or/34-43
45	31 not 44
46	24 and 45